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GRACE STUDY SUMMARY

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STUDY TITLE

Global Responses of Airborne Grass Pollen to Climate Change (GRACE)

STUDY SUMMARY

Grasses comprise over 40% of terrestrial species on the planet and grass (Poaceae) pollen is the major outdoor trigger of allergic respiratory disease. Changes in airborne Poaceae pollen in response to climate change have not previously been observed in large-scale studies, likely because grass diversity has been overlooked. Modelling suggests that air temperature and rainfall may differentially affect production of pollen by warm-season (C4) and cool-season (C3) grasses. Lumping these different types of grasses together and less attention to C4 grasses may have previously masked the ability to discern changes in airborne Poaceae pollen seasonality and load over time, and changes in Poaceae pollen dynamics in relation to climate change effects on grasslands. The aims of the **GRACE** study are (i) to investigate **how local environmental conditions influence spatial and intra-annual distributions in grass diversity globally** and (ii) to investigate **whether C4-rich sites exhibit different airborne Poaceae pollen season characteristics compared to C3-rich sites**. Importantly this study will (iii) investigate **whether airborne Poaceae pollen in C4-rich sites have different response to C3-rich-sites to air temperature and CO₂, as proxy for climate change**. Outcomes of this world-wide study will enable more nuanced tracking of Poaceae pollen exposure trends across continents and climate zones globally as terrestrial indicator metric of climate change with significance for managing human and planetary health.

Key References

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